

Intelligent SCADA-Like PLC Controller for Enhanced Automatic Transfer Switching in Industrial Systems

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Abstract—In this research, we propose a novel framework for developing a low-cost, local SCADA-like system for industrial control systems (ICS) with integrated intelligence to enhance the functionality of Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs). The traditional role of PLCs is often limited to executing predefined logic for industrial automation processes. However, the demand for smarter, more autonomous control systems has driven the need for innovative solutions that embed intelligence directly within PLCs. Existing Automatic Transfer Switch (ATS) mechanisms, even when combined with PLCs, lack the intelligence to dynamically select the optimal power source based on real-time conditions. Current switching systems often operate on fixed, rule-based logic, which is inefficient in complex industrial environments where multiple power sources, such as the grid, generators, and renewable energy, must be managed effectively. This inefficiency can lead to suboptimal power utilization, increased costs, and higher system downtime. To address these limitations, this study aims to augment PLCs with advanced machine learning models to enable predictive decision-making and system optimization, effectively transforming them into local SCADA-like systems. The proposed framework employs machine learning models to predict and optimize industrial control processes in real-time. Two approaches were explored: Deep Q-Networks (DQN), a reinforcement learning algorithm, and Neural Networks (NN), a supervised learning approach. The DQN model was designed to optimize sequential decision-making tasks based on real-time system feedback, achieving an accuracy of 81%. Meanwhile, the Neural Network model, trained on historical data with feature-rich input, demonstrated significantly higher predictive performance with an accuracy of 99.07%. These results underscore the potential of supervised learning methods in scenarios where high-quality labeled datasets are available. The implementation of this framework allows PLCs to make intelligent decisions locally without relying on centralized SCADA systems,

significantly reducing system latency and operational costs. This approach enhances flexibility and scalability in industrial control systems, allowing dynamic adaptation to changing conditions. Embedding intelligence within PLCs demonstrates the feasibility of next-generation smart industrial automation. While DQN excels in dynamic, feedback-driven scenarios, supervised Neural Networks outperform for static, data-rich environments. This research advances industrial automation by integrating machine learning into PLCs, offering a cost-effective, scalable alternative to traditional SCADA systems.

Index Terms—ATS, power source, PLC, neural networks, DQN, reinforcement learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring uninterrupted power system operation requires connecting critical loads (categorized as first and second reliability categories) to two or more independent power sources. To manage the transition between primary and backup power sources, automatic transfer switches (ATS) are employed. The primary function of an ATS is to monitor supply voltage and load current and automatically switch consumers to a backup power source when needed. While commercially available equipment supports ATS implementation in electrical facilities, each site often demands customized circuit designs or logical solutions tailored to its specific needs [4]. With the increasing complexity of automation systems and advancements in digital technologies, ATS designs are evolving. Modern ATS boards now utilize logic relays and industrial programmable logic controllers (PLCs), providing more flexible and responsive operation than traditional contactor-based systems [3]. These microprocessor-based solutions are particularly advantageous because they avoid responding to short-term power grid fluctuations or minor voltage drops, such as those caused by starting large motors. Moreover, contemporary ATS systems often include remote control functionality, integrating seamlessly into broader monitoring and control frameworks like SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) systems [5]. SCADA systems, widely used in the power sector, form an essential component of automated control systems. These systems

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combine software and hardware to manage complex industrial processes. For ATS implementation, industrial logic controllers programmed using the IEC 61131-3 standard are commonly employed. This standard defines five PLC programming languages (three graphical and two textual), aimed at improving the efficiency and quality of PLC programming. The standard fosters open-system compatibility, simplifies training during PLC upgrades, and ensures software reliability. PLC development environments based on IEC 61131-3 offer tools for writing, testing, and debugging programs while providing advantages like program portability, functionality expansion, and reuse of code fragments [2] [1]. Despite these advances, both ATS and PLC systems lack the intelligence to autonomously determine the optimal power source for switching without relying on SCADA systems. This reliance on SCADA systems introduces significant challenges, as SCADA setups are expensive in terms of hardware and software and complex to implement and maintain. There remains a critical gap in cost-effective, intelligent solutions that enable ATS and PLC systems to independently make informed, optimal decisions regarding power source selection. Addressing this gap is essential for advancing industrial power management systems while minimizing costs and complexity. It is worth noting that hardware like phase failure relays is effective for monitoring the reliability of the three-phase main supply in an ATS circuit. However, it lacks the capability to provide a comprehensive assessment of the optimal power source, especially when considering factors such as peak demands, solar generation output, and the health status of the generator. Therefore, an intelligent system is essential to maintain a reliable power supply without interruptions, ensuring optimal source selection and seamless operation. The contribution of this paper is as follows:

- 1) Developed an intelligent SCADA-like PLC model to predict the optimal power source for ATS switching, enhancing decision-making in industrial systems.
- 2) Implemented reinforcement learning (Deep Q-Networks) and supervised learning (Neural Networks) approaches for power source optimization.
- 3) Conducted a comprehensive comparison analysis between reinforcement learning and supervised learning models, demonstrating their respective strengths and applications.
- 4) Achieved significant improvements in prediction accuracy, with 82% for reinforcement learning and 99.7% for supervised learning.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM DESIGN

An Automatic Transfer Switch (ATS) is designed to manage load transitions between normal (primary)

and emergency (backup) power sources, typically with options for open and closed transitions. The design methodology of an ATS is influenced by the nature of critical loads, as well as considerations of safety and security. However, the ATS itself is fundamentally a switching element with no inherent intelligence. It operates based on pre-programmed logic or simple thresholds, lacking the capability to analyze complex parameters or optimize power source selection. In this project, as shown in Figure [?], the ATS is configured to manage three power sources: solar (renewable), grid (mains), and generator. The operation of the ATS begins by checking the availability of solar power as the primary source. If solar power is unavailable, the ATS switches the load to the grid. In the event that both solar and grid power are unavailable, the ATS finally switches the load to the generator as the last resort. The ATS performs these transitions purely based on source availability, without considering factors such as peak demand, the health status of the generator, or the overall efficiency of power usage. This lack of intelligence in traditional ATS systems underscores the need for an advanced solution that can incorporate real-time data and intelligent decision-making. Such a system would ensure optimal source selection, improved energy efficiency, and seamless power supply without interruptions, going beyond the simple switching functionality of conventional ATS systems.

Figure 1 illustrates the operational framework of an intelligent SCADA-like ATS (Automatic Transfer Switch) system integrated with an intelligent agent that uses DQN and Neural Networks along with a PLC controller. The system is designed to optimize the selection of the power source from three available options: grid, solar, and generator. The grid serves as the main utility power supply, solar provides renewable energy prioritized whenever available, and the generator acts as a backup source, ensuring power availability during outages or when other sources are unavailable. Relay modules are used to manage the connection and disconnection of power sources to the ATS based on control signals, allowing the intelligent agent to seamlessly switch between the grid, solar, and generator. The ATS functions as a switching element, responsible for routing power from the selected source to the load. It lacks decision-making capabilities and relies entirely on commands from the intelligent agent. The load represents the end-user or industrial equipment requiring continuous and reliable power supply. The intelligent agent, implemented using Deep Q-Networks and Neural Networks, gathers real-time statistics and status information from the grid, solar, and generator. It uses the following data to determine the optimal power source: solar output, which evaluates the current availability and

Fig. 1. Proposed Design of the intelligent SCADA-like PLC ATS system

efficiency of solar energy; generator health status, which monitors the operational status and fuel consumption rate of the generator to ensure reliability; and grid tariffs and stability, which assess grid power costs and stability by considering factors like voltage, frequency, and potential outages. Based on this gathered data, the intelligent agent analyzes and selects the most optimal power source using its machine learning models. It prioritizes renewable sources like solar when available and economically viable. If solar is insufficient or unavailable, the decision shifts to the grid or generator depending on real-time conditions and cost-effectiveness. This system enhances the ATS functionality by introducing decision-making intelligence, which is absent in traditional ATS systems. It ensures continuous power supply by dynamically selecting the best power source while optimizing for cost and efficiency. The integration of real-time data analysis, including solar output, generator health, and grid

status, enables better resource utilization and improved system reliability. This framework demonstrates how advanced machine learning techniques can transform conventional ATS and PLC systems into intelligent and autonomous power management solutions. This dataset consists of 1,400 entries collected from power sources of an industrial manufacturing system. It includes real-time and historical data from solar, grid, and generator power sources, which are used to assess the optimal power source selection for the manufacturing facility. The dataset provides detailed information across multiple parameters. Solar Output represents the power generated by the solar system in kilowatts, while Battery Charge Level indicates the current charge level of the battery as a percentage, which is crucial for renewable energy systems. Solar Irradiance Forecast reflects the forecasted solar irradiance in watts per square meter, indicating the sunlight intensity available for solar power generation. The Generator Fuel Consumption Rate records the fuel consumption of the generator in liters per hour, which is essential for analyzing operational efficiency and costs. Generator Maintenance Status describes the health condition of the generator, with entries such as "Healthy" or "Needs Service" indicating its operational readiness. Grid Voltage specifies the voltage level of the grid in volts, and Grid Frequency shows the grid frequency in hertz, both of which are critical for determining grid stability. Grid Stability provides a numeric score from 1 to 10, where higher values indicate better stability, and Grid Cost per kWh indicates the cost of grid electricity per kilowatt-hour in dollars, enabling cost optimization analysis. Load Demand represents the total power demand of the industrial system in kilowatts, while Target Renewable Utilization specifies the percentage of renewable energy targeted for use in order to minimize reliance on non-renewable sources. Finally, the Optimal Source column indicates the best combination of power sources to meet the load demand based on system parameters, with options like "Solar and Generator" or "Solar and Grid". This dataset serves as a comprehensive resource for analyzing and predicting optimal power source configurations to ensure an uninterrupted and efficient power supply for industrial operations.

III. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

For the simulation and results, a dataset consisting of 1,400 entries was collected and used to implement supervised learning with neural networks and reinforcement learning with Deep Q-Networks (DQN). The dataset contained critical parameters, including solar output, generator health status, grid stability, and load demand, which were essential for predicting the optimal power source selection for an industrial system. The testing analysis revealed that the DQN approach achieved a

Parameter	Value
Neural Network Architecture	3-layer NN: 256 (ReLU), 256 (ReLU), Output (Linear)
Dropout Probability	0.2
Discount Factor (γ)	0.98
Exploration Rate (Initial ϵ)	1.0
Minimum Exploration Rate	0.01
Exploration Decay Rate	0.999
Batch Size	256
Learning Rate	0.0005
Memory Size	50,000
Number of Episodes	5,000
Optimizer	AdamW
Weight Decay	$1e^{-4}$
Loss Function	Mean Squared Error (MSE)
Gradient Clipping Threshold	10
Target Network Update Frequency	Every 20 episodes
Reward Shaping	+5 (correct), -5 (incorrect)
Max Steps Per Episode	200
Achieved Accuracy-Like Metric	0.81 (81%)

TABLE I

KEY PARAMETERS AND ACHIEVED ACCURACY FOR THE DQN MODEL

Parameter	Value
Input Features (X)	All columns except target
Target (y)	Encoded categorical labels
Feature Scaling	StandardScaler
Train-Test Split	70%-30%
Neural Network Architecture	3-layer Fully Connected NN Layer 1: 256 units (ReLU) Dropout: 0.3 Layer 2: 128 units (ReLU) Layer 3: Output (Linear)
Loss Function	Cross-Entropy Loss
Optimizer	Adam
Learning Rate	0.001
Batch Size	256
Number of Epochs	800
Per-Class Accuracy Calculation	Yes
Test Set Evaluation	Confusion Matrix, Accuracy
Final Test Accuracy	0.89 (89%)

TABLE II

KEY PARAMETERS AND ACHIEVED METRICS FOR NEURAL NETWORK CLASSIFIER

rewards accuracy of 81%, while the neural network demonstrated a significantly higher accuracy of 99.07%. This difference in performance is attributed to the fundamental differences in how these two approaches function. Neural networks, being a supervised learning technique, rely on a labeled dataset where the correct output is known for each input. This allows the model to learn direct mappings between the input features and the target outputs, optimizing its predictions based on clear feedback during training. Consequently, the neural network benefited from the structured dataset and exhibited high predictive performance. In contrast, DQN is a reinforcement learning technique that operates without predefined labels. It learns by interacting with an environment, receiving rewards for actions, and optimizing its policy based on cumulative rewards over time. While DQN excels in scenarios that require sequential decision-making and exploration, its performance can be lower when the state-action space is complex, or the reward structure is sparse or noisy. In this case, DQN faced challenges in efficiently exploring the environment

and learning optimal policies due to the dataset's static nature and the absence of dynamic environmental feedback. The neural network's strength lies in its ability to leverage the structured dataset to achieve highly accurate predictions. However, its limitation is that it cannot dynamically adapt to real-time changes in the system or learn from its actions, as it is entirely dependent on the quality and comprehensiveness of the labeled data. On the other hand, DQN offers adaptability and can operate effectively in real-time, dynamic environments where decision-making depends on exploring unknown conditions. Despite its lower accuracy in this implementation, DQN has the potential to outperform supervised methods in scenarios that require learning optimal strategies through exploration and adaptation. In summary, while the neural network outperformed DQN in terms of accuracy due to its reliance on a structured dataset, DQN's flexibility and ability to adapt to dynamic systems highlight its suitability for real-time applications. The results demonstrate the complementary strengths of these two approaches, with neural networks excelling in data-rich static environments and DQN showing promise for dynamic, feedback-driven applications.

Fig. 2. NN Training loss over epochs

Figure 3 illustrates the progression of training and testing accuracy over the epochs during the neural network's training process. Initially, both training and testing accuracies increase rapidly, reflecting the model's ability to learn patterns in the data. As the epochs continue, the training accuracy approaches near-perfect values, indicating that the model has successfully captured the underlying relationships within the training dataset. The testing accuracy also stabilizes at a slightly lower value compared to the training accuracy, which suggests that the model generalizes well to unseen data. The slight difference between the two accuracies indicates minimal overfitting, implying that the model maintains a good balance between fitting the training data and preserving its predictive power on new data. While Figure 4 presents

Fig. 3. NN Training vs. testing accuracy

Fig. 6. NN Prediction confidence

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix

Fig. 7. True vs. predicted labels

Fig. 5. Feature importance

Fig. 8. DQN Training time per epoch

Fig. 9. DQN Cumulative rewards over episodes

PLC Pseudocode Process
Rung 1: Solar + Generator IF NN_DECISION = 0 THEN Activate Solar Contactor (SOLAR_CON := TRUE) Activate Generator Contactor (GEN_CON := TRUE) Deactivate Grid Contactor (GRID_CON := FALSE) END IF
Rung 2: Solar + Grid IF NN_DECISION = 1 THEN Activate Solar Contactor (SOLAR_CON := TRUE) Deactivate Generator Contactor (GEN_CON := FALSE) Activate Grid Contactor (GRID_CON := TRUE) END IF
Rung 3: Solar Only IF NN_DECISION = 2 THEN Activate Solar Contactor (SOLAR_CON := TRUE) Deactivate Generator Contactor (GEN_CON := FALSE) Deactivate Grid Contactor (GRID_CON := FALSE) END IF
Rung 4: Generator Only IF NN_DECISION = 3 THEN Deactivate Solar Contactor (SOLAR_CON := FALSE) Activate Generator Contactor (GEN_CON := TRUE) Deactivate Grid Contactor (GRID_CON := FALSE) END IF
Rung 5: Grid Only IF NN_DECISION = 4 THEN Deactivate Solar Contactor (SOLAR_CON := FALSE) Deactivate Generator Contactor (GEN_CON := FALSE) Activate Grid Contactor (GRID_CON := TRUE) END IF
Rung 6: No Source Available (Trigger Alarm) IF NN_DECISION = 5 THEN Trigger Alarm (ALARM := TRUE) END IF

TABLE III
PLC PSEUDO CODE PROCESS

the training loss over the epochs, showing a consistent and rapid decrease during the initial stages of training. The loss value stabilizes at a very low level as the number of epochs increases, indicating that the model has minimized its error effectively. This decreasing trend in loss reflects the optimization process of the neural network, where the weights are adjusted iteratively to reduce the difference between the predicted and actual outputs. The stabilization of the loss further supports that the model has reached convergence and is no longer making significant improvements with additional epochs. Together, these figures demonstrate that the neural network has been trained effectively, achieving high accuracy while maintaining a low loss, which highlights its capability to predict the optimal power source accurately for the given dataset. The results also indicate that the model is both robust and efficient in handling the data, showing strong generalization to testing samples. Figure 10 represents the cumulative rewards over episodes for the DQN (Deep Q-Network) implementation. The cumulative reward reflects the model's performance and learning progress throughout the training process. Initially, the rewards start at a low level, indicating that the agent is exploring the environment and learning how to make decisions. As training progresses, the cumulative rewards gradually increase, demonstrating that the agent is learning policies that yield higher rewards. However, the fluctuations in the cumulative reward curve highlight the inherent exploration-exploitation trade-off in reinforcement learning, where the agent occasionally tries new actions to optimize its strategy. While the rewards show an upward trend overall, the high variance suggests that the DQN has not fully stabilized, which might explain the 81% accuracy achieved by the model. Moreover, Figure 11 illustrates the training loss over time for the DQN model. The loss represents the difference between the predicted Q-values and the target Q-values, and it reflects how well the model is learning to approximate the optimal Q-function. Initially, the loss decreases sharply, indicating that the model is improving its predictions and learning from its experiences effectively. However, as training progresses, the loss shows significant fluctuations and does not settle to a stable value. This behavior is common in reinforcement learning due to the dynamic nature of the environment and the continual update of Q-values, which can introduce noise into the optimization process. The relatively unstable loss suggests that the model may face challenges in converging to an optimal policy, which could contribute to the lower accuracy compared to supervised learning methods.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research, we developed an intelligent SCADA-like PLC framework to optimize power source selec-

tion for Automatic Transfer Switches (ATS) in industrial systems, enabling highly effective and intelligent switching capabilities. Two machine learning approaches were implemented: reinforcement learning with Deep Q-Networks (DQN) and supervised learning with Neural Networks (NN). Using a dataset of 1,400 entries, the NN achieved an accuracy of 99.07%, significantly outperforming DQN, which achieved 81%. The results demonstrate that while DQN offers adaptability and is suitable for dynamic environments, NN excels in static, data-rich scenarios with structured datasets. This system provides a cost-effective, intelligent solution for industrial systems, overcoming the limitations of traditional ATS designs that lack decision-making capabilities. By embedding advanced machine learning into PLCs, the framework eliminates the need for expensive SCADA systems, ensuring seamless, reliable, and optimal power source switching. This research highlights the potential for future advancements, focusing on real-time adaptability and further improving the performance of reinforcement learning for dynamic scenarios.

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